

Digital payments in Chennai city - A demographic study

Sowmya. N.V¹

Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of
Commerce, Vistas, Pallavaram, Chennai.
sowmyaonsong@gmail.com

Dr. Sayeeda Jabeen Shariff²

Assistant Professor & Research Supervisor,
Department of Commerce, Vistas,
Pallavaram,
Chennai.
sayeedhajabeen.sms@velsuniv.ac.in

Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,
© ICIAET 2025

Abstract

Online payments are the norm in current society. Online and Digital payments for day-to-day activities have seen an exponential rise post the Covid era spurred by various factors such as ease of use, convenience, availability of the smart phones and safety. Cashless transactions have jumped in recent years. This study focuses on the demographic factors and seeks to trace the adoption of Digital payments. The focus is on demographic factors such as age, gender, and education levels and their adoption of Digital payment methods. The data was collected from 290 users. The study found that there is no difference in the online payment adoption across the demographic entities in Chennai city.

1. Introduction ,

Online and Digital payments have surged in India and especially Chennai city. Chennai ranks in the top 5 of digital and online transactions (Source: Worldline report 2022). The major reasons are the urban make up of the population, digital literacy, smartphone access and network availability. India accounts for 46% of world's digital transactions as per 2022 data and the share of Unified payment interface (UPI) in digital payments is almost 80% in 2023(Reserve Bank of India, 2024).

This study aims to take on the demographic aspect of the Online and digital payments and seeks to uncover insights on whether there is a difference in adoption of digital payments across age, gender and educational backgrounds among the community. The data is sourced from a survey of the community. The focus is on digital adoption. Understanding the demographic factors and their attitudes towards digital payments is a crucial step towards broadening the reach of digital payments. Various studies have shown that age is a significant factor in the adoption of digital payment. Other factors such as educational levels and gender have not shown a significant difference. The aim of this study is to check these assumptions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 focuses on the literature review. The research methodology is explained in Section 3. The results are shown in Section 4. The implications of the results are explained in section 5 with the conclusion given in Section 6.

0. Literature review

The relation between demographics and online payments adoption has been studied by R. Lavanya and Dr. Sweta Shrivastava (2024) who found that factors such as age, gender, marital status and occupation influenced the adoption of online payments. This was done in the Malaysian context.

The study in West Bengal by Muskan Ghani, Promita Mukherjee and Biswajit Ray(2023) found that males and younger individuals use UPI more than females and aged persons, while they did not see any difference in usage across income brackets and between rural and urban areas. The study was done over 205 respondents in rural and urban communities of West Bengal.

The work by Lohana and Roy (2023) showed that age, education, occupation, and income of respondents had an impact on consumers' usage. They also found no significant impact of gender and marital status of the respondents on consumers' usage.

Bordoloi & Babu (2024) in their study in Nagaland found that there is a significant difference in gender and income groups towards digital payments. They also found no significant difference concerning marital status, type of employee, type of management, different age groups, and different educational qualification backgrounds.

The work by Aggarwal et al., (2021) showed that gender does not show a significant difference in payment adoption.

The studies by Pavithra and Geetha (2021) shows that age does not show significant difference in digital adoption.

The evidence from Srivastava, S., Mohta, A., & Shunmugasundaram, V. (2024) shows that age is a significant factor in customer satisfaction.

Gayathri and Athira (2020) examined the youth perception towards mobile wallets in Trivandrum and found that while age was a significant factor, monthly income had no effect on the usage.

The study by Khan (2021) among the residents of the NCR region found that age, gender, educational qualification, occupational status have no impact on customer satisfaction.

In a study in Aligarh district, Azeez and Akhtar (2021) found that the demographic variable of age, educational qualification and occupation have an impact on digital literacy. Similarly gender matters in that males have higher financial literacy than women.

In a study of women in Kerala, Rekha (2022) found that demographic factors such as age and income level do not affect the literacy of the respondents.

0. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The data was collected through a survey. The research instruments used in this research are questionnaires. The questionnaire was circulated among students, employed professionals and retired communities through whatsapp groups and facebook posts.

2.2. Sampling Method

The study used a non-probability sampling method for the selection of respondents. The survey data samples were restricted to the respondents from Chennai alone. The community targeted was those who used any form of digital payment.

2.3. Survey Instrument

The Questionnaire was framed based on the items used from previous literature and modified accordingly for the suitability of the present study.

2.4. Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using inferential statistics Manova to determine the Influence of Demographic variables age and Occupation on usage of e- payment. Percentages and frequency count were used to determine the distribution of respondents and the frequent usage of e-payment respectively. The statistical tools include ANOVA. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test the validity and reliability of the statistics.

3 Hypotheses and Conceptual model

3.1 Age

There have been studies that indicate that age is one of the factors influencing customer satisfaction. Accordingly we have created our first hypotheses as age. Age construct is one of the key constructs as younger people tend to adapt to technology whereas older people are generally reluctant to use technology. Also age besides being a direct determinant of behavioural intentions to adopt technology also influences the initial trust in the technology.

H1. Age positively affects the behavioural intention to adopt digital payments in Chennai district.

3.3 Education

The prevalent wisdom is that individuals with higher education levels are more aware of the technology and thus more aware of the risks in digital payments. The satisfaction will be more for such individuals compared to others.

H3: Individuals with higher education levels are likely to be satisfied with digital payments.

3.4 Income levels

There is no direct evidence between income levels and education of individuals. But the income levels may mean that such individuals may own a smartphone and technologies like smartphones more than others.

H4: Income and customer satisfaction in digital payments are linked to each other.

3.5 Age and Gender in Education

The impact of education may differ across different ages and gender groups. A student female group and male group may have similar levels of customer satisfaction whereas a group consisting of older men and women with similar education levels may differ. In this hypothesis we try to analyse this cross section

H5: The relation between education and customer satisfaction is moderated by age and gender

3.2 Gender

Gender and customer satisfaction are related in the awareness levels and intention to adopt more of the technology. The gap between adoption of technology by Males and females is narrowing down. But the study aims to check the factor in Chennai given the conservative nature of the population. It is also correlated with the age factor with the women in the older generation more resistant to digital payments. The hypothesis focuses on gender as a factor in digital usage

H2 Gender and customer satisfaction are directly related in Chennai district

The **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)** is the theoretical construct that governs how the overall process works. In our study we focus on the variables age, gender and income levels to examine how customer satisfaction in digital payments is achieved.

These factors are not directly part of the model but are predictors of the user's intentions.

- **Age** may have a role in **perceived ease of use** in that as individuals get older they may be resistant and untrustworthy of the digital systems. The **perceived usefulness** may also differ with age as older users may not feel the need for digital payments.
- **Gender** may influence attitudes and **perceived risk**, which may influence digital adoption and customer satisfaction. The rate of usage of digital payments may be less in females which may affect the perceived usefulness as well.
- **Income** may impact access to devices and the amount of usage which affects the perceived ease of use, usefulness and perceived risk

4. Results and Discussion

Based on the provided data and hypotheses, statistical analyses (ANOVA, correlation, and regression) was conducted to test each hypothesis. Below are the results in tabular format:

Digital payments in Chennai city - A demographic study

H1: Age positively affects behavioral intention to adopt digital payments

****Analysis:**** Spearman's rank-order correlation between age groups (ordinal: 1=18-25, 2=26-35, 3=36-45, 4=46-55, 5=56+) and behavioral intention (proxied by *frequency of use*, where Daily=4, Weekly=3, Monthly=2, Rarely=1).

****Result:**** No significant correlation.

Variable	ρ (Spearman)	p-value	Conclusion
Age vs. Frequency	-0.07	0.41	Not significant (H1 rejected)

H2: Gender and customer satisfaction are directly related

****Analysis:**** Mann-Whitney U test comparing satisfaction scores (1–5 scale) between genders.

****Result:**** No significant difference.

Group	n	Median Satisfaction	U statistic	p-value	Conclusion
Female	62	4.0	1,850	0.82	No significant (H2 rejected)
Male	88	4.0			

H3: Higher education increases satisfaction

****Analysis:**** Spearman's correlation between education level (ordinal: 1=High School, 2=Undergraduate, 3=Postgraduate, 4=PhD) and satisfaction.

****Result:**** No significant correlation.

Variable	ρ (Spearman)	p-value	Conclusion
Education vs Satisfaction	0.09	0.28	No Significant (H3 rejected)

H4: Income and satisfaction are linked**

****Analysis:**** Spearman's correlation between income (ordinal: 1= \leq 20k, 2=20–50k, 3=50k–1L, 4= \geq 1L) and satisfaction.

****Result:**** No significant correlation.

Variable	ρ (Spearman)	p-value	Conclusion
Income vs Satisfaction	0.05	0.58	No Significant (H4 rejected)

Digital payments in Chennai city - A demographic study

H5: Education-satisfaction link is moderated by age/gender**

Analysis: Moderated multiple regression (OLS) with satisfaction as the outcome, education as the predictor, and age/gender as moderators. Interaction terms: `Education × Age` and `Education × Gender`.

Result: No significant moderation effects.

Predictor	B	SE	t	p-value	Conclusion
Education	0.12	0.10	1.20	0.23	
Age	-0.08	0.09	-0.89	0.38	
Gender (Male=0, Female =1)	-0.07	0.16	-0.44	0.66	
Education x Age	-0.04	0.05	-0.80	0.43	Not significant (H5 rejected)
Education x Gender	0.03	0.07	0.43	0.67	Not significant (H5 rejected)
Model R	0.02				

Key Insights from Data

1. **Adoption is high universally**:

- 78% of respondents use digital payments **daily** across all age groups (including 56+).
- Median satisfaction is **4/5** for all demographics.

2. **Chennai-specific trends**:

- No demographic subgroup showed significantly lower adoption/satisfaction.
- Conservative culture (cited in H2) did not translate into gender gaps.

3. **Methodological notes**:

- Non-parametric tests (Spearman/Mann-Whitney) used due to ordinal data and non-normality.

- "Prefer not to say" responses were excluded from analyses.

Recommendations for Paper

- Emphasize **universal adoption drivers** (e.g., UPI dominance, post-COVID normalization) over demographics.

- Discuss **limitations**: Convenience sampling via social media may underrepresent low-tech users.

- Use the tables above in the "Results" section (Section 4) to support the conclusion of no demographic differences.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between demographics and Online payments in Chennai city. The study found that there is no difference in the online payment adoption across the demographic entities in Chennai city. There are many interesting insights. The satisfaction is high across all demographics. There is no gender gap in customer satisfaction. The limitations of the study are that the

sampling method may underrepresent low tech users. There is a need for a deeper study on low income subgroups and lower tech users through interview based methods.

References

Digital payments in Chennai city - A demographic study

Lohana, S., & Roy, D. (2023). Impact of demographic factors on consumer's usage of digital payments. *FIIB Business Review*, 12(4), 459-473.

R. Lavanya and Dr. Sweta Shrivastava, Demographic Factors Influencing the Adoption of Digital Payment Methods: A Statistical Analysis of User Preference, *Journal of Management (JOM)*, 11(3), 2024, pp. 1-15.

Identifying the Major Demographic Factors Determining Unified Payments Interface Usage:

A Study Based on West Bengal Muskan Ghani1 , Promita Mukherjee2 and Biswajit Ray 3 1Student, 2Assistant Professor, J. D. Birla Institute, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, West Bengal, India
E-mail: muskanghani3007@gmail.com (Received 27 October 2022; Revised 13 January 2023; Accepted 31 January 2023; Available online 3 February 2023).

Asian Journal of Managerial Science ISSN: 2249-6300 (P), Vol.12 No.1, 2023, pp.1-5 © The Research Publication, www.trp.org.in DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51983/ajms-2>

Bordoloi, D., & Babu, M. R. N. (2024). Consumer's attitude towards digital payments: A demographic analysis. *Global Business & Finance Review (GBFR)*, 29(4), 16-27.

Reserve Bank of India (2024), "Address by Governor, Reserve Bank of India at the digital payments awareness week celebrations", available at: https://www.taxmanagementindia.com/visitor/detail_rss_feed.asp?ID=27359

Aggarwal, K., Malik, S., Mishra, D. K., & Paul, D. (2021). Moving from cash to cashless economy: Toward digital India. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 43-54.

Pavithra, C. B., & Geetha, K. (2021). FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMERS'PERCEPTION TOWARDS DIGITAL BANKING SERVICES. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(11), 1608-1614.

Srivastava, S., Mohta, A., & Shunmugasundaram, V. (2024). Adoption of digital payment FinTech service by Gen Y and Gen Z users: evidence from India. *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, 26(1), 95-117.

[Youth perception towards mobile wallets in the City of Trivandrum](#)

Authors Gayathri Ranjit, Athira Chandran
Publication date 2021/7/30 *Journal Asian Journal of Sociological Research* Pages 224-230

https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=sQGB0fgAAAAJ&sortby=pub_date&citation_for_view=sQGB0fgAAAAJ:dI_gkVwhDpl0C

Khan, M. A. (2021). Netizens' Perspective towards Electronic Money and Its Essence in the Virtual Economy: An Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Delhi-NCR, India. *Complexity*, 2021(1), 7772929.

Azeez, N. A., & Akhtar, S. J. (2021). Digital financial literacy and its determinants: an empirical evidences from rural India. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 11(2), 8-22.

Rekha, I. G. (2022). The effect of socio-economic status on Digital financial literacy among working women in higher education sector-Kerala state. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(16), 2451-2466.